

Rapid On-Site Evaluation of Endoscopic Pulmonary Biopsies with Artificial Intelligence

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Abstract. Rapid On-Site Evaluation (ROSE) enables a preliminary evaluation of cytological samples from endobronchial or transbronchial biopsies, allowing clinicians to predict sample adequacy and determine whether additional examination is needed. However, this assessment is highly dependent on the clinician's experience. Since Artificial intelligence (AI) has demonstrated considerable potential in supporting other visual diagnostic processes, this study presents a preliminary evaluation of an AI model to assist a clinician at ROSE by automating the analysis of cytological smears obtained from fine-needle aspirations or biopsies of pulmonary lesions and lymphadenopathies.

Keywords: Rapid On-Site Evaluation, bronchoscopy, diagnosis.

1 Introduction

Rapid On-Site Evaluation (ROSE) is a key technique for the real-time assessment of cytological samples obtained during endobronchial or transbronchial biopsies [1, 2]. This approach enables a preliminary evaluation of sample quality, allowing clinicians to determine whether additional sampling is necessary. As such, ROSE enhances both the accuracy and efficiency of the sampling procedure. However, the assessment of cytological preparations during ROSE is highly dependent on the experience of the personnel performing the evaluation. This critical interobserver variability may lead to incorrect sample evaluations and delay in diagnosis [2]. Even though Artificial intelligence (AI) has demonstrated considerable potential in supporting diagnostic processes across various medical disciplines that rely on imaging techniques, including

cytopathology [3], no study has applied AI models to the enhancement of ROSE. Addressing this gap, this study is a preliminary work aimed at the development and validation of software for the automated analysis of ROSE cytological smears obtained from fine-needle aspirations or biopsies of pulmonary lesions and lymphadenopathies.

2 Materials & Methods

This work presents a retrospective study with prospective validation. An AI model has been trained on a preliminary database 210 histopathology slide images obtained via bronchoscopy from suspected thoracic lesions (such as consolidations and nodules), following definitive diagnosis.

2.1 Data Collection

The cytological samples were collected using standardized ROSE procedures during bronchoscopy [4, 5]. The cytological material was smeared on pre-labeled slides, fixed in 95% ethanol, and stained with Toluidine blue. Slides were sent to the pathology department for an in-depth cytological and immunohistochemical analysis. The slides have been preliminary classified by clinicians. Each sample has been assigned to one of the following diagnostic classes:

- Negative slides (74 samples, SLIDES NEG)
- Adenocarcinoma-positive slides (112 samples, SLIDES POS_ADK)
- Squamous cell carcinoma-positive slides (11 samples, SLIDES POS_SCC)
- Micro-positive slides, rare malignancy (13 samples, SLIDES POS_micro)

Only samples with adequate cellularity and complete diagnostic documentation have been included in the database. To ensure sample quality, selected slides have been re-evaluated by expert cytopathologists. Then, slides have been scanned at high resolution using a histological slide scanner, generating digital files in analysis-compatible formats (e.g., .svs, .tiff). All slides have been anonymized using numeric identifiers, ensuring full compliance with data protection regulations.

2.2 AI Model

A subset of the digitized slides (training set, 80% of the total samples) has been used to train the AI model, which aims at automatically classifying slides into the four diagnostic categories. A separate subset of slides (validation set, 20% of the total samples), not used during training, has been used to assess diagnostic performance. Metrics include sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) for each class.

The samples show typical limitations of histopathology datasets: a limited number due to the need for human pre-classification; class imbalance, with rare classes being underrepresented; and model overfitting. Due to severe class imbalances, minority classes (SLIDES POS_SCC and SLIDES POS_micro) provided insufficient training data, leading to prediction challenges. To increase diversity in the training data, data augmentation was applied. Augmentations included rotations (randomly rotation of $\pm 30^\circ$), shifts (width and height shifts up to 20%), shearing (geometric shear transformations), zooming (random zooming of up to $\pm 30\%$), horizontal flipping (mirror along the

horizontal axis), and brightness adjustment. MobileNetV2, a lightweight convolutional neural network pre-trained on ImageNet, is here proposed due to its efficiency at learning with smaller, less complex datasets. The transfer learning setup used the ImageNet pre-trained MobileNetV2 as the backbone, with the feature extraction layers frozen initially to retain ImageNet knowledge. A custom classification head was appended with a flattening layer, a dense layer with 128 neurons and ReLU activation, a dropout layer (rate 0.5) to reduce overfitting, and a final dense layer to predict outputs using the softmax activation function:

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{\exp(z_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^n \exp(z_j)} \quad (1)$$

where \hat{y}_i is the probability of class i , z_i is the raw output score, and n is the number of classes.

Sparse categorical cross-entropy loss was used to guide the optimization process, measuring the difference between the true label and predicted probability for the correct class as

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \log(\hat{y}_{i,t}) \quad (2)$$

where N is the total number of samples and $\hat{y}_{i,t}$ the predicted probability of true class t for sample i . This penalizes incorrect predictions with higher loss values, incentivizing the model to predict true labels correctly. Finally, to address severe class imbalance, class weights were applied during training to ensure minority classes contribute more to the total loss, mitigating bias toward the majority class (SLIDES POS_ADK).

3 Results & Discussion

The model achieved a validation accuracy of 41%, highlighting significant performance disparities across classes, with minority classes performing poorly. The weighted average F1-score across classes was 0.39. The classification metrics for each class are summarized in Table 1, while the confusion matrix in Table 2 characterizes the model's misclassification across classes. The high confusion between SLIDES NEG and SLIDES POS_ADK reflects overlapping visual characteristics, while minority classes (SLIDES POS_SCC and SLIDES POS_micro) are severely misclassified, with most predictions biased toward SLIDES POS_ADK. As shown in Fig. 1, training loss decreased significantly in the first 10 epochs and converged to ~ 1.13 by epoch 25, whereas validation accuracy fluctuated below 45%, peaking at 41%, indicating slight overfitting due to limited dataset size.

The results of this preliminary study were overall promising, showing the potential of AI in analysing slides for ROSE. However, the study also highlighted the limits of the preliminary dataset, with 210 images being insufficient to train MobileNetV2 effectively and exacerbating overfitting. Further, minority classes were neglected due to limited representation and the overlapping features of SLIDES NEG and SLIDES POS_ADK made separation harder. In future work, we anticipate the use of synthetic data generation (SMOTE/GANs) to create a more balanced datasets could significantly improve the AI model. Alternatively, focal loss could be implemented to emphasize classification of difficult, minority-class samples.

Fig. 1. Training accuracy and loss over epochs.

Table 1. Classification metrics.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support	Notes
SLIDES NEG	0.29	0.22	0.25	74	Low recall highlights difficulty in distinguishing negatives from positives.
SLIDES POS_ADK	0.51	0.62	0.56	112	Good performance due to its majority representation in the dataset.
SLIDES POS_SCC	0.12	0.09	0.11	11	Poor performance caused by insufficient samples.
SLIDES POS_micro	0.00	0.00	0.00	13	No learning occurred for this rare minority class due to its underrepresentation.

Table 2. Confusion matrix.

Actual \ Predicted	NEG	POS_ADK	POS_SCC	POS_micro
NEG	16	42	10	6
POS_ADK	28	70	9	5
POS_SCC	3	7	1	0
POS_micro	7	5	1	0

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the potential of AI models in ROSE techniques for thoracic endoscopy, and, in particular, highlights how MobileNetV2 can be adopted for histopathology slide classification with small medical datasets. While reasonable results were achieved for majority classes, minority classes suffered from poor recall due to imbalanced representation. Future efforts should focus on collecting larger

datasets and employing advanced data balancing techniques to improve overall classification performance.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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